

The Impact of Training Need Analysis (TNA) on Employee's Performance: An Analysis Made on Five-Point Likert Scale

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ABSTRACT

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is a crucial step in identifying performance gaps and determining training requirements. This study investigates the impact of TNA on employee performance and to examine its impact on employee engagement, motivation, and overall job satisfaction. A mixed-method including qualitative and quantitative approach has been used by combining surveys and interviews with trainees of training institute. In this research total of 120 cooperative extension officers' (CEO) Govt of Bihar and 30 Training professionals from Training Institute DNSRICM, Patna participated in the research. A well-structured self-evaluation questionnaire with the five-point Likert scale for survey was carried out to the primary data. This study will help to identify the relevance of training needs, leading to increased engagement and motivation, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability among employees, enhancing job satisfaction through targeted skill development, encouraging a culture of continuous learning and growth. The study highlights the importance of integrating TNA with employee experience initiatives, ensuring that training programs address specific needs and concerns. By doing so, organizations can create a more supportive and developmental work environment, leading to increased employee retention and overall

success. These findings are significant to design training manuals as a part of professional development which will help to enhance personnel efficiency and lead for the benefits of organization.

1. Introduction: Training Need Analysis is the process of identifying training needs in an organization for the purpose of improving employee job performance. It includes to deliver the right training in the right way to the right people. The most fundamental aspect of human resource management is training. It is the methodical use of formal procedures to assist individuals in gaining the information and abilities required to carry out their tasks in a satisfactory manner ARMSTRONG'S HANDBOOK OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICE (n.d.). The primary approach to accomplishing institutional objectives is through training. It enhances the performance of both the employer and the employee.(Ghafoor Khan et al., 2011). Employee performance is influenced by a variety of factors, including job satisfaction, organisational policies, working conditions, interaction with colleagues, and training. Consequently, training is one of the most effective methods for improving employee performance and achieving organisational objectives and goals in a timely and effective manner(Aktar et al., n.d.). TNA is an essential component of the training and development process that takes place during the initial planning phase. It is a strategic process that includes the identification of organisational objectives, the collection and analysis of competency data, and the identification of potential voids between the current situation and future requirements (Horng & Lin, 2013; Khan & Masrek, 2017; Tao et al., 2006) Conducting TNA for an organisation is an essential component of the job analysis and performance analysis. It is generally accepted that the implementation of TNA would be an effective approach to enhance the efficacy of training programs. Personnel would never be capable of enhancing their knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA) unless their training requirements were accurately assessed. Therefore, it is undeniable that the performance of an employee is not solely dependent upon TNA; it can also be influenced by socioeconomic factors, including the employee's age, educational status, the type of training they receive, and their mobility. Undoubtedly, age is a significant demographic factor that is strongly correlated with the level of satisfaction, task contribution, and monetary rewards of its employees(Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2019). "Learning of skills, concepts, or attitudes that result in progress in the process environment as a whole" is one expression that may be used to describe training. The evaluation of training wishes is present in all aspects of the operational area of work. This is done in order to determine the standards and positions of the human elements of the machine in an

effective manner and to address training that is appropriate. The Training needs Analysis (TNA) is an ongoing process that involves gathering data to determine what training requirements are now, with the end goal of designing training that will assist the organisation in accomplishing its objectives. TNA provides considerable information and assists in the design of the training program in the appropriate manner. Before developing any training program for the development of personnel, an organisation is required to undertake a training requirement analysis (Mamun, 2021). Staff training alone might not be sufficient to satisfy some non-existent criteria or priorities. TNA supports the business in the areas where these resources—such as increased knowledge, increased abilities, and a positive attitude—will have the major impact on employees' personal development. TNA increases confidence in success by improving organisational performance as well as employee performance. Self-efficacy, experience, mastery orientation for post-training, educational principles, and post-training interventions were training success variables linked to post-training attitudes. (Mamun, 2021)

Steps	Analysis	Contents
1	The Origin	Trainers should identify the crucial components of creating a well-structured organisational problem and systematically work towards generating a problem.
2	Specify Object with Needs	Once a training requirement has been determined, the subsequent objective is to ascertain the underlying reasons of the issue. Subsequently, training modules might be utilised for personnel who possess insufficient skills.
3	Confirm the Needs	It is important to clearly define the training goals, purposes, and needs before proceeding with the training modules.
4	Design Training Modules	Subsequently, the training framework and modules are designed in accordance with the specified criteria. The training content design should be closely aligned with the problem at hand.
5	Evaluations	A training manager can assess the impact of training by comparing the expected outcome based on the training course with the actual results observed after the training. Furthermore, the costs associated with training can be estimated and incorporated into the training planning

Table 1: TNA Procedure

The research study will offer an insightful information on how employee performance is influenced by motivation, teamwork, training, and motivation. This paper's primary goal is to investigate the impact of training need analysis (TNA) on employee performance, given its significance. Intending to provide a response to the query of how useful training requirements analysis is in determining training needs, outlining the objectives of the program, carrying it out, and assessing its effectiveness. The goal of the study is to go further and look into how TNA affects performance from the viewpoint of the employee. The research aims to:

Demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between TNA and the following:

- Identifying training needs, defining the goals of training programs, assigning training to the desired employee, the process of training implementation, training evaluation, and employee performance evaluation.
- Determine the impact of TNA on employee performance.
- Follow-up on the efficacy of training requirements analysis in the context of employee job responsibilities.
- Comprehend the complete benefits of training to need analysis for an employee.

2. Literature Review: Since training is based on what is needed, figuring out the amount, type, and length of the training is the most important thing at this point. So, figuring out what training an organisation need is the diagnostic step in planning its goals. According to (Khan & Masrek, 2017) Training requirements assessment is a strategic process that entails the identification of the organisation, industry objectives, competency acquisition, and data analysis to identify the discrepancies between the current and prospective conditions. The assessment stage entails performance issues related to both employees and employers in order to determine whether training is required. Non-training factors, including compensations, organisational structure, job design, and physical work plans, must be taken into consideration during the assessment.

(Horng & Lin, 2013)The performance of employees is significantly influenced by TNA practices, including the identification of training impact, training type, and training impacts. In this investigation, the author in this study has enhanced comprehension of the manner in which the components of TNA practices supplement employees' job performance. The practical implications for human resource administrators will assist in the development and support of employee job performance, which will ultimately support the growth of the organisation.

The author of this paper demonstrated that employee performance had a positive relationship with training effectiveness and training need analysis. In addition, he elaborated that employee competency serves as a partial mediator between employee performance and training functions. (Mahmood et al., 2018)The author recommended the implementation of training programs, as it has an impact on employee performance and competency, and prioritised training need analysis and training effectiveness as part of the planning process.

The primary objective of this research was to analyse the impact of training needs assessment (TNA) on the performance of employees within an organisation. The author attempts to elucidate the efficacy of the training needs analysis in an organisation, which is instrumental in the establishment of a positive organisational image and the attainment of organisational objectives. The researcher also analysed the impact of training needs assessment (TNA) on the performance of personnel within an organisation(Kura & Kaur, n.d.).

In this study researcher investigated the relationship between TNA and employee performance with president paint Nigeria Limited in Ojokoro. The author collected primary data and total respondents were 98 employees from production and administrative department. (Adefisayo, n.d.)In the study, the researcher discovered that training needs analysis makes it possible to transform the identified needs into learning goals. Further the author concluded the research by giving recommendations in order to make training need more efficient by applying the formula of to make an appropriate training policies by management, to show consistency in training practices, and top management should also take participate in delivering training practices which will help to enhance inclusivity among organization members.

3. Research Methodology: The study used a mixed method approach includes both primary and secondary data. Primary data collection includes a well-structured self-evaluation questionnaire with the five-point Likert scale for conducted for a pilot survey. A described research strategy used. Systematic sampling methods was used to collect the sample. 120 of personnel were selected for sample regarding training at the institute for the research and 30 training professionals were selected separately for the survey. Secondary data was collected through online published content i.e. google scholar, sci hub, research gate, semantic scholar. The purpose of the study was explained to them, and they were requested to provide honest responses to the questionnaire. The data has been recorded, tabulated, and summarised.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 4: Summary of Professional Trainer's Responses on TNA Practices

	Questionnaire	Total	Strongly Agree (%)	Total	Agree (%)	Total	Disagree (%)	Total	Strongly disagree (%)	Point
1	Management uses a structured process to find TNA.	18	60	10	33.3	8	26.6	0	0	2
2	Management obtains feedback from employees in order to determine the TNA.	5	16.6	3	10	15	50	0	0	1
3	Management Value and support Training	25	83.3	20	66.6	4	13.3	1	3.3	3
4	Managers Ensure that workers have the necessary training.	16	53.3	10	33.3	5	16.6	1	3.3	3
5	Appropriately approved training program by management	18	60	15	50	6	20	0	0	2
6	The participants are provided with pre-training information by the management.	1	3.3	1	3.3	15	50	0	0	0
7	Management appropriately assesses the training program.	22	73.3	15	50	5	16.6	0	0	3
8	Management believes training improves employee skills, talents, and knowledge.	25	83.3	20	66.6	6	20	0	0	5
9	Management finds TNA training useful.	27	90	21	70	5	16.6	0	0	4
	Total		100		100		100		100	

The sample questionnaires used for the study of TNA from training professionals are displayed in Table 4. Thirty training specialists in all took part in the training need analysis evaluation. There are nine items in all on the questionnaire to assess performance with regard to training need analysis. Respondents'

responses were stated on a five-point Likert scale, with alternatives such as strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. The assessment technique used a five-point Likert scale. For data evaluation, a straightforward percentage technique has been employed. The observation above indicates the favourable opinion of the training need analysis process. While the majority of respondents focused on the advantages of training need analysis. Five-point The Likert scale is a most prominent used tool for assessing attitudes and opinions.

The results show that in the chosen industries, formal performance indicators are used to identify the training needs. If the management in the chosen industries conducts a proper Training Needs Analysis (TNA), 83.3% not only believe that training can increase employees' skills, abilities, and knowledge, but 90% also find training to be effective. According to the survey, management will ensure that employees are receiving the training 53.3% meant to transmit if 60% identify TNA through recognised procedures and another 60% approve a fair training program. Conversely, the survey indicates that 16.6% of respondents provided inadequate responses regarding the identification of TNA by management through employee feedback, which must be addressed appropriately.

Fig 1, T4

Table 5: Summary of Respondent's Response on TNA Practices

	Questionnaire	Total	Strongly Agree (%)	Total	Agree (%)	Total	Disagree (%)	Total	Strongly disagree (%)	Point
1	The present training programs are satisfactory to the employees.	55	45.8	40	33.3	15	12.5	0	0	3
2	Employees perceived that the training was important to their personal and organisational objectives.	50	41.6	55	45.8	10	8.3	0	0	3
3	The training program is contextually pertinent to the employees.	60	50	70	58.3	7	5.8	0	0	3
4	Employees perceive training as advantageous during their actual duties.	80	66.6	60	50	0	0	0	0	4
5	They are aware of the high-level management's concerns regarding training effectiveness and TNA.	75	62.5	70	58.3	11	9.1	0	0	4
6	Before training, employees' skill deficiencies are accurately identified.	45	37.5	30	25	20	16.6	0	0	2
7	Employees perceive that training effectiveness is	83	69.1	66	55	10	8.3	0	0	5

	significantly influenced by TNA.								
	Total		100		100		100		100

The sample questionnaires used for the study of TNA from personnel who received training are displayed in Table 4. 120 trainees took part in the training need analysis evaluation. There are 7 items in all on the questionnaire to assess performance with regard to training need analysis. According to the point Likert scale technique, respondents gave the present training program an average rating of 3 out of 5. The most important recommendations made by the respondents were to update the training modules to reflect current and future requirements and to include more realistic and situational games in the training process, since they will boost cognitive capacity as well.

Fig 1. T5

Fig 2. T5

Fig 3. T5

Fig 4. T5

Fig 5. T5

Fig 6. T5

Fig 7. T5

Table 6: Sample Characteristics of Trainees

Variables	No. of Observations	No. of Categories	Categories				
Gender	120	2	Female			Male	
Educational Qualifications	120	4	Diploma	Bachelors	Masters	Ph.D.	
Years of Experience	120	5	Below 2	2-5	5-10	10-20	>20

Table 7: List of Questionnaires

S. No	Dimension and Items	Y/N
1	Training Type	
Q1	Management’s advice for training to secure a promotion	Y
Q2	A Refresher Training session was organised	N
Q3	Aware of the Training requirements for current job position	Y
Q4	Induction training was organised during joining	Y
Q5	Level of satisfaction during training (S.A/A/D. A/SD. A)	Y
2	Training Goals	
Q1	Management offers training options related to job positions	N
Q2	Prior to my attendance, Training manager informed me of the training's efficacy	N
Q3	By participating in job training, I acquire new competencies and skills	Y
Q4	Training motivates me to operate more proficiently.	Y
Q5	By enhancing my task management abilities, training enhances my productivity at work.	Y
Q6	Training helps me develop new and current talents.	Y
Q7	Training boosts satisfaction with work.	Y
Q8	The training strategy accelerates my professional progress decisions.	Y
Q9	Training impact & influence your performance? 1. Work efficiency and productivity 2. Employee satisfaction	Y

Tables 6 and 7 above display the questionnaire list and an example of a trainee's characteristic during the training orientation. If we analyse the response rate, we can conclude that the efficacy of training is contingent upon the analysis of training needs. Finally, after analysing the response rate of both trainer and trainees it may be concluded that TNA has an impact on training efficacy.

5. Conclusion: The main aim of this study was to evaluate the influence of training on employee performance. The study has effectively achieved its research aims. According to the study's findings, the training aspects (training needs assessment, design, delivery style, and evaluation) have a notable and beneficial impact on employee performance. In conclusion, it can be stated that the training aspects have a substantial impact on the performance of individuals inside these organisations. Training has the ability to modify behaviour and attitude, regardless of age, and contributes to the expansion of organisational operations. The organisation should provide assurance and facilities during training, as well as off-the-job training. Employers facilitate the enhancement of their workers' skills by organising training sessions. If the quality of the training is excellent, the human resources will use their utmost effort to accomplish the objectives of the organisation. To enhance the effectiveness of training programs, it is crucial to improve the efficiency of conducting training needs analysis. This study reveals that workers from various departments demonstrate a greater level of sincerity in completing Training Needs Analysis (TNA) prior to organising any training session. This commitment to TNA significantly enhances the efficacy of the training. Based on the research findings, it is advised that future researchers should focus on developing effective tools and procedures for Training Needs Analysis (TNA) on a broader scale. This would facilitate the design of training programs for employees with enhanced efficacy.

Authors Declaration:

The author disclosed no potential conflicts of interest.

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